

Pedagogical Competence of Islamic Education Teachers Based on The Perspective of Indonesian Law Number 14 of 2005 Concerning Teachers and Lecturers

Muhajir Abd. Rahman

Department of Islamic Education, Institut Agama Islam Negeri Ambon, Ambon, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

Published Online: July 15, 2024

This research examines the challenges Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City face in meeting academic qualification standards and pedagogical competencies by Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers. Even though there are continuing education and training programs, many teachers must meet the minimum Bachelor or Diploma IV qualifications. This research highlights the importance of deep understanding and educational insight for teachers in their teaching assignments. Teachers with solid theoretical knowledge are more effective in applying diverse learning methods and adapting material to student characteristics, thereby improving the quality of teaching. A good understanding of the curriculum, application of innovative learning methods, and the ability to adapt to individual student needs are essential to creating an effective and inclusive learning environment. This research shows that teachers' ongoing efforts to improve the quality of their learning can significantly influence educational outcomes. However, teaching practices still need improvement, especially in innovation and adaptation of learning methods.

KEYWORDS:

Pedagogy, Islamic Religious Education, Law, Competence

1. INTRODUCTION

The realization of teachers who have competencies that can boost the quality of national education requires serious attention from various groups. The government, as the most responsible party, has issued various policies related to improving the quality of education, including Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturer, Republic of Indonesia Government Regulation Number 19 of 2007 concerning National Education Standards. However, let us look at the actual conditions that exist. We can see the gap between the policies implemented and the results achieved in the government's efforts to improve the quality of Indonesia's human resources, including the quality and caliber of teachers. Therefore, through the Ministry of National

Corresponding Author: Muhajir Abd. Rahman

**Cite this Article: Muhajir Abd. Rahman (2024). Pedagogical Competence of Islamic Education Teachers Based on The Perspective of Indonesian Law Number 14 of 2005 Concerning Teachers and Lecturers. International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies, 4(7), 731-738*

Education, the government plans to have an intelligent and competitive Indonesian society by 2025 (Dodi Nandika, 2021).

This idea aims to answer challenges and become a reference and strategic step to answer future demands. This strategic policy can only be implemented if education is a human investment force and social and human capital, which will play a role in the formation and transformation of culture and if the empowerment process is managed professionally. To handle education professionally, the role of educational staff is vital in addition to adequate facilities and costs. Why are educational personnel so important? Historian Henry Adams in Dodi Nandika sees that teachers are so influential that they do not know when their influence will end (Dodi Nandika, 2021).

Therefore, the government must have the courage to design and implement programs that can directly or indirectly improve teacher quality, including (1) advanced study programs, (2) deepening knowledge, (3) improving skills, and (4) holding discussions. Between teachers. Teacher. Teacher. Friends, and (5) work environment exchange. Advanced study programs are prioritized for teachers without minimum academic qualifications. These teachers have not or are still receiving high school, D2, and D3 education, including

Muhajir Abd. Rahman, Pedagogical Competence of Islamic Education Teachers Based on The Perspective of Indonesian Law Number 14 of 2005 Concerning Teachers and Lecturers

elementary, middle school, and high school teachers who have yet received education. Bachelor's Degree (S1). Teachers who do not yet have a bachelor's degree (S1) are required to take part in a further education program, as mandated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers article (8): Teachers must have academic qualifications, competencies, teaching certificates, and be physically healthy. Spirituality and can realize national education (Undang-undang (UU) Nomor 14 Tahun 2005 tentang Guru dan Dosen, 2005)

Article (8) above emphasizes that every teacher must have academic qualifications. The academic context refers more to the educational qualifications that teachers must have. Teachers must take further education up to bachelor's level as an academic requirement. University teachers follow the academic activities to obtain undergraduate education qualifications. It is further explained in article 9 that "academic qualifications as referred to in article 8 are obtained through higher education in undergraduate programs or fourth diploma programs" (Undang-undang (UU) Nomor 14 Tahun 2005 tentang Guru dan Dosen, 2005).

All teachers appointed by the government as teachers, and those who still need to be teachers must have a minimum academic qualification of a bachelor's degree or fourth diploma obtained through learning activities at a university. The teacher education qualification process to obtain minimum education (first degree) is carried out at universities as institutions with the authority to produce professional and competent teaching staff in their fields. Therefore, teacher academic qualifications are pursued through formal education activities as explained in the regulation of the Minister of National Education of the Republic of Indonesia Number 16 of 2007 concerning Academic Qualification Standards and Teacher Competencies, an attachment to the Minister of National Regulation. Education Number 16 of 2007 dated 4 May 2007: that teacher academic qualifications are formal education units including PAUD/TK/RA, SD/MI, SMP/MTs, SMA/MA or other equivalent forms of teacher education, must have a minimum educational qualification four diploma (D-IV) or undergraduate (S1) study programs by the subjects taught/taught, and obtained from accredited study programs (Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, 2007)

Academic qualifications and teacher competence are absolute requirements that a teacher and Islamic religious education teacher must have. Islamic religious education teachers as elementary/middle school/high school/vocational school subject teachers are required to have competence in interpreting the material, structure, concepts, and mindset of sciences that are relevant to Islamic religious education learning, as well as analyzing the material, structure, concepts, and mentality of science. -knowledge that is relevant to learning Islamic religious education (Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan, 2007)

Not all Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City have academic qualifications as mandated by law. Because there are still Islamic religious education teachers at the primary school level who have a second diploma. Meanwhile, based on the author's observations, the competencies required by law still need to be implemented optimally, namely pedagogical and professional competencies as mandated by law. Regarding the academic qualifications of Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City, not all of them have undergraduate qualifications (S1). The number of Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City is 108, with details of 43 elementary school teachers, 18 middle school teachers, and 47 high school teachers.

Of the 108 Islamic religious education teachers mentioned above, all high school-level Islamic religious education teachers have met the first-level academic qualification standards. At the same time, Islamic religious education teachers in junior high schools have met first-level academic qualifications and diploma requirements. Only one person does not have a bachelor's degree (first degree) or four diploma qualifications. However, when this research was conducted, the person concerned attended a college program. In contrast to Islamic religious education teachers in elementary schools, Of the 43 people who have met the academic qualification requirements, 24 still need to meet the academic qualification standards. When this research was conducted, they were currently studying at the Tarbiyah and Teacher Training Faculty of IAIN Ambon.

In its existence, Islamic religious education teachers also have a strategic role in educating and educating the nation's children. Apart from these requirements, Islamic religious education teachers also function as spiritual fathers (Eliyawati et al., 2023). Islamic religious education teachers teach their students knowledge and how to direct students to have noble character and always be close to Allah SWT. Therefore, Islamic religious education teachers are required to have competency abilities as required by Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, namely pedagogical competence, where teachers, including Islamic religious teachers, are expected to have the ability to understand students. In-depth and carry out appropriate learning. Educate. Student understanding includes an understanding of student developmental psychology. Meanwhile, educational learning involves designing, implementing, and assessing learning processes, outcomes, and continuous improvement. It is realized that the task of Islamic religious education teachers is also to teach Islamic religious education fields of study or subjects in the schools where they work (Hanaysha et al., 2023)

In this regard, the author is interested in analyzing Islamic religious education teachers' pedagogical competence and professional competence from the perspective of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning

Muhajir Abd. Rahman, Pedagogical Competence of Islamic Education Teachers Based on The Perspective of Indonesian Law Number 14 of 2005 Concerning Teachers and Lecturers

Teachers and Lecturers. Based on the author's observations of the circumstances and conditions of Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City, they seem to have not fully mastered and applied pedagogical and professional competencies in learning activities. Not yet maximizing pedagogical competence means implementing educational and dialogical learning, utilizing learning technology, learning planning, and understanding the insights or foundations of education.

II. METHOD

In this research, qualitative research was used with a phenomenological approach. The phenomenological approach is an approach that is based on phenomena or facts that occur naturally in the field and does not require researcher intervention (Pham, 2022). This method is used because qualitative research begins with phenomena that arise in the research setting (research location) without any interpretation. Even so, the facts are seen as they are without being engineered by researchers. The various data sources are all based on phenomena seen from various attitudes, actions, and symptoms displayed by the sources/informants. In this case, the researcher observed all attitudes, actions, and actions carried out by Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City before, starting, and after learning activities.

To obtain valid, complete, and accurate data and information, researchers use two types of data sources, namely primary data sources and secondary data sources (Ajayi, 2023). The primary data referred to in this research is in the form of information/data from informants or data sources in the research field, namely from Islamic religious education teachers, school principals, other teachers, and school administration staff. He also supervises Islamic religious education teachers from the Ministry of Religion of Ambon City/Kanwil of the Ministry of Religion of Maluku Province and the Ambon City Education and Sports Office. Meanwhile, secondary data is supporting data obtained from literature (research libraries) such as books, magazines, journals, newspapers, and other sources considered relevant to this research's content and objectives.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Understanding Insight or Basic Education

Islamic religious education teachers with insight and an excellent educational foundation will understand how to carry out their duties well. The theoretical knowledge he obtained during the educational process or lectures was sufficient for him to carry out his school teaching profession. His ability to apply theoretical knowledge in class through learning activities broadens the understanding and insight he honed during college (Eliyawati et al., 2023). Therefore, teachers of Islamic religious education must uphold scientific principles and scientific truths in learning activities. This means that Islamic religious education teachers use theoretical

principles, such as approaches, strategies, methods, and learning techniques, to educate subjects creatively in carrying out learning activities at school, especially in the classroom. (An interview with the Head of SMA Negeri 13 Ambon, Ambon, 5 April 2023).

Islamic religious education teachers with good educational insight and theoretical understanding of education will have implications for the learning process. The teacher's ability to understand theoretical knowledge impacts changes in students. Learning is a complex student action and behavior (Mursyida et al., 2022). Therefore, this is only experienced by the students as an act of learning. Students are the determinants of the success or failure of the learning process. The learning process occurs because students gain something from what is in their surrounding environment. Even though students are considered a determining factor in the learning process, students are not the only factor in education. There are many other factors, such as the presence of teaching staff, environment, learning methods, facilities and infrastructure, and learning objectives. Several educational determinants are factors that determine the success of the learning process. (An interview with the Head of SMP Negeri 14 Ambon, Ambon, 16 April 2023.)

Relevant to the interview data above, the following also presents the results of observations of several Islamic religious education teachers who carry out learning activities in the classroom. The person concerned is seen reviewing the lesson material calmly and enthusiastically. This can be seen from his attitude and appearance in front of the class. His cheerful face showed that he was very enthusiastic. His voice, sometimes loud and sometimes soft, shows that he is absorbing what is being taught. The description of the subject matter presented shows that he mastered the subject matter being taught. He is not angry with his students, although his male students sometimes annoy each other. In a soft and modest voice, he admonished him not to disturb his friends, destroying the ongoing learning atmosphere.

Students with potential and talents are different from each other. Therefore, it is necessary to have insight into the knowledge or educational foundation of an Islamic religious education teacher so that students are not positioned as objects of education but as subjects of education. When teachers position students as objects of education, the perception is that they are like empty barrels that must be filled. This principle places students as having no potential and talent lower than they were born. However, when Islamic religious education teachers position students as educational subjects, then students have several inherent potentials and talents (Dodi Nandika, 2021). Teachers must grow and develop this potential through academic activities and classroom learning. Students have different characteristics from each other. Different characteristics require different attention and approaches. Even though the education system still applies a classical system, Islamic religious education

teachers must pay special attention to their students in the learning process.

On the one hand, Islamic religious education teachers pay attention to all students in the learning process in class; on the other hand, Islamic religious education teachers must pay special attention to specific students. Therefore, Islamic religious education teachers must master the principles of learning well. Several principles that need to be mastered by Islamic religious education teachers include the principle of attention, the principle of activity, the principle of apperception, the principle of demonstration, the principle of repetition, the principle of correlation, the principle of concentration, the principle of individualization, the principle of socialization, and the principle of evaluation (Meira, 2020; Stimpson & Calvert, 2021)

Learning activities carried out by Islamic religious education teachers at SMA Negeri 13 Ambon and Islamic religious education teachers at SMA Negeri 5 Ambon show that raising students' attention to learning is the application of the principle of attention and the principle of correlation. Therefore, the learning activities carried out require the ability of each teacher to arouse students' learning attention, whether in the form of deliberate attention caused by the influence of Islamic religious education teachers or spontaneous attention arising from the students themselves. Teachers as intentional generators of attention, need to teach as interestingly as possible, such as mastering the subject matter, using engaging learning media, providing healthy distractions, and mastering the learning atmosphere so students are focused.

When teaching in class, the Islamic religious education teacher at SMP Negeri 14 Ambon applies the principle of activity by using coercion as a process in learning activities in class. Students are divided into four groups. Each group is invited to make a script according to the discussion points recorded on the blackboard. The subject matter of Islamic religious education is fascinating, so students always enjoy participating in learning activities in class. This Islamic religious education teacher at SMP Negeri 14 invited his students, divided into four groups, to create a script according to their perception and understanding of the existing material. Students can be seen creating scripts calmly through discussion while writing them down in each group's notebook. Next, each participant is taught in their group to read their script and then record it in the group notebook before reading it on behalf of the group to be presented in front of the class on behalf of their respective groups. This atmosphere applies generally to all groups. After completing between twenty-five and thirty minutes, the Islamic religious education teacher invited the first group to come to the front of the class to demonstrate the results of the text description. With enthusiasm and occasionally interspersed with dialogue with laughter and colorful jokes between fellow groups, participants were directed to show their skills in acting out

dialogue fragments and filled with a friendly atmosphere. After the first group demonstrated and explained the results of their group work formulation, the second, third, and fourth groups continued. After each group has finished presenting the results of their group work formulation, the Islamic religious education teacher provides additional explanations and explains the meaning contained in the fragment the students have just finished presenting. Finally, the Islamic religious education teacher concludes the lesson material for his students.

From various learning activities as a form of applied understanding and foundation of education, Islamic religious education teachers have demonstrated their ability to utilize them in learning activities. Learning is a complex action and behavior of students because learning is only experienced by students. The learning process occurs because students, including teachers, obtain something from the surrounding environment (Ben-Eliyahu, 2021). Apart from that, students have different characteristics from each other, so they require different attention and approaches. Even though the learning system still applies the classical system, teachers must pay special attention to students in the learning process.

On the other hand, teachers must pay special attention to all students in the class; Teachers must also pay special attention to specific students. Therefore, Islamic religious education teachers must master the learning theories and principles formulated by the Malang Methodical Didactic Team, namely the principle of attention, the principle of activity, the principle of apperception, the principle of demonstration, the principle of repetition, and the principle of learning. Correlation principle, concentration principle, individualization principle, socialization principle, and evaluation principle.

However, based on observations by researchers, Islamic religious education teachers still need to understand the insights and foundations of education sufficiently. This can be seen from the fact that Islamic religious education teachers still need to implement learning rules in the form of learning principles such as individualization and correlation.

Student Understanding

Learning activities will run well if all learning activities influence each other. The elements in question are teachers, students, media, methods, learning objectives, indicators, and evaluation. Teachers have a strategic role in directing the learning process as a factor that controls the course of learning activities. Therefore, Islamic religious education teachers are required to understand the above factors well. Students, as individuals who are growing and developing, have different characteristics from each other (Sailer et al., 2021).

When researchers conducted classroom observations, the Islamic religious education teacher explained the lesson material while referring to the learning program plan. Being

guided by the learning program plan is the proper provision for Islamic religious education teachers. This is because the understanding of student development in the classroom can be seen from the results of researchers' observations at SD Negeri 79 as follows: Islamic religious education teachers carry out learning activities while still paying attention to the differences in the characteristics of their students. These differences include intellectual differences. Intellectual differences are visible when learning occurs, where Islamic religious education teachers carry out learning evaluations and patiently guide students who cannot answer questions. Student participants who cannot answer these questions are directed to return to the lessons taught under the guidance and direction of the Islamic religious education teacher. Apart from that, students are directed to study at home through guidance provided by each student.

The differences in characteristics of students as individual creatures cannot be denied. Therefore, every teacher, including Islamic religious education teachers, must understand and know them more deeply. Every individual has differences and similarities. These differences include interests, talents, motivation, desires, and attention. Its meaning consists of the desire to progress and change. Apart from that, every individual's self-confidence and wanting to be appreciated are inherent. Children are not miniature adults. It is said that because physically, he is different from adults. Likewise, psychologically, he is different from adults (Liu et al., 2022)

For this reason, children are free to get what they want to develop optimally according to their abilities, talents, and interests. In the learning process, students are the center of attention. Students want to be human, as is the goal of education itself. The humane goals described in educational goals must be by the child's image. What is the nature of children as students? How do children's minds develop as students so they can be well educated? An Islamic religious education teacher needs to master and understand educational psychology, developmental psychology, and learning psychology adequately (Gralewski, 2019).

The learning atmosphere is going well. Students enthusiastically sing under the guidance of Islamic religious education teachers. This condition shows that students are very involved with their world. The teacher's ability to immerse himself in the world of children who love to play gives the impression that every child (student), especially at the elementary school level, loves to play. There is nothing wrong with teachers being able to immortalize this icon by creating an atmosphere of learning while playing. Students at the elementary level enjoy playing (Sunandar et al., 2022; Yusuf et al., 2023). Creating an atmosphere when learning is very relevant to each child's character, including elementary school students such as those at SD Negeri 23 Ambon who like to play. Learning activities using various methods, including learning while playing or singing, will arouse

students' learning motivation. Students are stimulated to express their potential while playing in the learning corridor. Understanding the nature of the world of children (students) is an inseparable part of the success of learning activities in the classroom.

However, it is realized that not all Islamic religious education teachers understand the characteristics of students well. For example, when carrying out learning activities, there are Islamic religious education teachers who carry out learning activities that seem monotonous. This means that learning activities take place in one direction. Islamic religious education teachers are more active in dominating learning activities. The lecture method he uses makes students seem passive. Students only hear and accept the teacher's explanation. This was discovered when researchers made observations at SMA Negeri 13 Ambon. The use of the lecture method in learning activities with teacher dominance should not occur if the Islamic religious education teacher understands the characteristics of his students. Students should be placed as educational subjects with the potential to be developed by Islamic religious education teachers through the academic stimulation and teaching they receive. Not only Islamic religious education teachers at SMA Negeri 13 Ambon; there are also similar things at SMP Muhammadiyah Ambon. Islamic religious education teachers carry out learning activities mainly using the lecture method. Therefore, students appear restless, and their concentration during learning is slightly disturbed. This condition lasts from the beginning to the end of the learning activity. However, this does not mean that the lecture method is not allowed. Even so, Islamic religious education teachers should use various learning methods, so students stay energized when participating in learning activities. Even though students are seen sitting quietly in their respective seats, their learning concentration could be more focused on the teacher's explanation. His thoughts have scattered abroad, and he no longer concentrates on class lessons.

Lesson Plan

Islamic religious education teachers, like teachers in general, are responsible for planning learning (Suharsongko et al., 2023). The learning planning in question includes preparing annual plans, semester plans, course plans, and weekly and daily plans. The most important thing an Islamic religious education teacher must do is in the form of a weekly plan and lesson materials. The weekly plan relates to the teacher's readiness to prepare learning tools that will be implemented for the learning process before implementation. Meanwhile, learning plans in subjects are more about learning preparation in the form of learning program plans that will be implemented in classroom learning activities. (An interview with an Islamic Religious Education Teacher at SD Negeri 6 Ambon, April 15, 2023). April 15: The usefulness of learning activities is related to many factors. Starting from

initial planning preparation, implementation of learning activities in class, and evaluation. The three have a close relationship that cannot be separated. It is an integrated system that influences each other.

Good learning planning will correlate with the level of achievement of learning activity results in the future. Initial planning of learning activities includes preparing learning programs such as syllabi and learning program plans. (results of an interview with an Islamic Religious Education Teacher at SD Negeri 6 Ambon, April 15, 2023). April 15 With lesson planning, Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City also cannot fail to use appropriate methods. Methods, often called methods, techniques, and strategies, have a significant role in learning activities. Generally, learning activities are carried out by teachers at school using appropriate methods to achieve the goals that have been set. This means that the determination of the method is adjusted to the material or content of the teaching material. The lecture method can be used if the material is about explaining concepts. Likewise, if the subject of discussion is prayer, the method used differs from the lecture demonstration and question-and-answer method. The existence of methods in learning activities determines the achievement of learning outcomes and objectives. Selecting and using methods appropriate to the subject matter will make it easier for students to understand. On the other hand, if the method used is not appropriate to the material being taught, it will make it difficult for students to understand the lesson material.

The dominance of Islamic religious education teachers who use conventional methods does not mean they do not know active learning strategies but do not want to change (Suharsongko et al., 2023). At that time, the researcher conducted a free interview with one of the Islamic religious education teachers with the question, "Why not use active learning strategies like those that have developed recently?" (An interview with an Islamic Religious Education Teacher at SD Negeri 89 Ambon, April 14, 2023).

Thousands of data from April 14 above show that Islamic religious education teachers still need more innovation in preparing learning tools. There are strong indications that Islamic religious education teachers, as mentioned above, need more responsibility and have very low creativity. Weak creativity and low responsibility also often cause them to use conventional methods.

Teachers understand that learning will be fun and exciting if learning methods stimulate students to be more actively involved (Lennert da Silva, 2021). Learning activities more oriented towards teacher domination are no longer relevant to development. On the other hand, it is time for learning activities to be directed at more active students than teachers. Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City are also aware of this. Several informants interviewed by researchers said that Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon realized that changes toward active learning strategies must

be made when carrying out learning activities. This awareness was born because they had participated in training activities during certification activities. One of the training materials is active learning strategies. After returning from training activities, all teachers are expected to be able to apply the material obtained in training activities during learning.

Role-playing in groups and individually makes learning activities exciting and more accessible for students to understand the existing learning material. Students' ability to build a solid and cohesive team shows students' ability to work together to achieve the set learning goals. Learning activities that involve students will stimulate students to be more vital in learning. It is realized that the teacher's ability to create learning designs by fully involving them is in line with human nature, which tends to play. While playing, there is nothing wrong with the learning design carried out by Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City, such as at SMP Negeri 14 Ambon. Playing, in this case, is, of course, in the context of learning.

Apart from that, when the author observed regular classes, it was seen how Islamic religious education teachers carried out learning activities relaxedly. This means that when learning activities take place, students are fully involved in learning activities. They are given a vast space to construct understanding by improvising through materials or teaching materials. Teaching materials use the sociodrama method to guide students in understanding the learning material. Students are actively involved in creating concepts about the material being taught. They enthusiastically created short drama concepts in their notebooks. After completing the drama concept, each group was invited by the Islamic religious education teacher to come to the front of the class to read the drama concept that had been prepared. When the first group finished presenting their task, the second group continued, and so on, until all groups had their turn to perform.

From the staged fragments, all students looked cheerful and enthusiastic in following the lesson material presented by the Islamic religious education teacher. After the drama performance, the Islamic religious education teacher summarizes the material and explains to students that they should not imitate commendable attitudes. Moreover, they should imitate commendable behavior in everyday life. If students are directly involved in learning activities, they will also learn how to behave and practice Islamic teachings in everyday life.

Thus, the learning planning activities of Islamic religious education teachers in Ambon City are likely suitable. As Tight in Jamal Ma'mur Asmani stated, learning planning is a series of delivery of learning materials to students so that they can receive, respond to, master, and develop learning materials. It is a way and process of reciprocal relationships between students and teachers. Who are both active in carrying out activities. Learning must be an active process for

Muhajir Abd. Rahman, Pedagogical Competence of Islamic Education Teachers Based on The Perspective of Indonesian Law Number 14 of 2005 Concerning Teachers and Lecturers

students to build their knowledge, not just a passive process that only receives explanations from the teacher about their skills. Teachers must create a learning atmosphere, so students actively ask questions and present ideas. This means that there is a connection between language and thought (Asmani, 2009).

Playing and exploring can help with brain development, language, reasoning, and socialization. Fun learning focuses full attention on education, so the attention span is high. Apart from that, students are also encouraged to interact actively and positively in groups. They know without pressure. The learning model Islamic religious education teachers use in Ambon City is cooperative learning, which refers to learning principles involving students with various abilities to work together in groups to achieve common goals. The emphasis is on students working together in groups to develop life skills such as finding and solving problems, making decisions, thinking logically, communicating effectively, and working together. The teacher's role in this context is as a facilitator. When students receive services from teachers by utilizing all the potential and talents that exist in them, they will develop and grow into independent students because the teacher provides as much space as possible without being dictated by the teacher (Aida, 2023).

IV. CONCLUSION

Islamic Religious Education Teachers in Ambon City still face challenges in achieving academic qualification standards and pedagogical competencies mandated by Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers. Even though there are efforts to improve quality through further education and training programs, many teachers still need to meet the minimum academic qualifications of S1 or D-IV.

Deep understanding and vital educational insight in Islamic religious education teachers is fundamental in their teaching duties. Teachers with solid theoretical knowledge effectively apply various learning methods that suit students' needs. They are also better able to adapt learning materials to the diverse characteristics of students.

Success in education not only depends on students' abilities but is also greatly influenced by the quality of teaching provided by teachers. Understanding the curriculum, implementing innovative learning methods, and adapting learning to individual student needs is critical to creating an effective and inclusive learning environment.

The regular and practical application of learning principles such as activity, attention, individualization, and teacher evaluation can facilitate a more profound and sustainable learning process. In addition, the active involvement of students in the learning process, such as through group discussions and project-based activities, is also essential to improve understanding and retention of material.

This research shows that although there are still challenges in teaching practice, especially regarding innovation and adapting appropriate learning methods, teachers who continue to strive to improve the quality of their learning can make a significant difference in educational outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Aida, S. (2023). Impact of E-Learning Orientation, Moodle Usage, and Learning Planning on Learning Outcomes in On-Demand Lectures. *Education Sciences*, 13(10).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13101005>
2. Ajayi, V. O. (2023). A Review on Primary Sources of Data and Secondary Sources of Data. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 2(3).
3. Asmani, J. M. (2009). *7 Kompetensi guru menyenangkan dan profesional* (N. Lubis, Ed.). Power Books (Ihdina).
4. Ben-Eliyahu, A. (2021). Sustainable learning in education. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(8).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13084250>
5. Dodi Nandika. (2021). *Pendidikan Di Tengah Gelombang Perubahan* (M. Fadjar, Ed.). LP3ES.
6. Eliyawati, Widodo, A., Kaniawati, I., & Fujii, H. (2023). The Development and Validation of an Instrument for Assessing Science Teacher Competency to Teach ESD. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(4).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su15043276>
7. Gralewski, J. (2019). Teachers' beliefs about creative students' characteristics: A qualitative study. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 31.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2018.11.008>
8. Hanaysha, J. R., Shriedeh, F. B., & In'airat, M. (2023). Impact of classroom environment, teacher competency, information and communication technology resources, and university facilities on student engagement and academic performance. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 3(2).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijime.2023.100188>
9. Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan. (2007). Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Nomor 16 Tahun 2007 tentang Standar Kualifikasi Akademik dan Kompetensi Guru. In *Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Nomor 16 Tahun 2007 tentang Standar Kualifikasi Akademik dan Kompetensi Guru* (pp. 1–16). JDIH BPK.
10. Lennert da Silva, A. L. (2021). Comparing teacher autonomy in different models of educational governance. *Nordic Journal of Studies in Educational Policy*.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/20020317.2021.1965372>

11. Liu, M., Gorgievski, M. J., Qi, J., & Paas, F. (2022). Increasing teaching effectiveness in entrepreneurship education: Course characteristics and student needs differences. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2022.102147>
12. Meira, D. (2020). Projections, connections and instruments of the cooperative principle of education, training and information in the Portuguese legal system. *Boletim de La Asociacion Internacional de Derecho Cooperativo*, 57. <https://doi.org/10.18543/BAIDC-57-2020PP71-94>
13. Mursyida, A., Rahman, R., Yulianti, F., & Taufan, M. (2022). Islamic Religious Education Teacher Learning Methods During the Covid-19 Pandemic Period in Junior High Schools. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research of Higher Education*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.24036/ijmurhica.v5i2.129>
14. Pham, S. T. H. (2022). The distinctions of Heideggerian phenomenological research method. *Qualitative Research Journal*, 22(2). <https://doi.org/10.1108/QRJ-09-2021-0093>
15. Sailer, M., Schultz-Pernice, F., & Fischer, F. (2021). Contextual facilitators for learning activities involving technology in higher education: The Cb-model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106794>
16. Stimpson, B., & Calvert, I. (2021). Qur'anic educational philosophy: Foundational principles of education in Islam's holiest text. *Religions*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12020082>
17. Suharsongko, M. E., Munawiroh, M., & Suharwanto, S. (2023). Competence of Islamic Religious Education Teachers from The Perspective of the Quran. *Journal of World Science*, 2(8). <https://doi.org/10.58344/jws.v2i8.397>
18. Sunandar, A., Efendi, M., Ediyanto, E., Thahar, M. M., Ulfah, N. H., Adha, M. A., Lailiyah, N., & Firdiana, A. D. (2022). HEALTHY SCHOOL MANAGEMENT MODEL OF CHILD-FRIENDLY SCHOOLS: CHILDREN NUTRITION STATUS AND LEARNING ATMOSPHERE. *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Management*, 10(2).
19. Undang-undang (UU) Nomor 14 Tahun 2005 tentang Guru dan Dosen. (2005). Undang-undang (UU) Nomor 14 Tahun 2005 tentang Guru dan Dosen. In *JDIH BPK* (pp. 1–36). JDIH BPK.
20. Yusuf, O. Y. H., Aprianti, F., Mayasari, D., Satriwati, S., & Balula, W. E. (2023). Educator and Student Interaction in a Classroom Learning Atmosphere. *AURELIA: Jurnal Penelitian Dan Pengabdian Masyarakat Indonesia*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.57235/aurelia.v2i1.309>